

Knowledge and Personal Safety Skill of Children in Banda Aceh

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Abstract— The objective of this research is to examine the relationship between knowledge about protection from sexual violence with personal safety skills in elementary school children. This research used survey model that involved 125 students from one elementary school in Banda Aceh and was taken by using a simple random sampling technique. Data was analyzed using Pearson correlation techniques. The results showed that there was a relationship between knowledge about protection from sexual violence with personal safety skills in elementary school students in Banda Aceh. The higher the knowledge, the higher the personal safety skills of elementary school students in Banda Aceh. These result can be used as a guide for further research on factors that can correlate with personal safety skills and make interventions to improve personal safety skills.

Keywords— Personal safety skills, knowledge, child.

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, sexual violence is a very alarming phenomenon in Indonesia. In 2019, the number of sexual violence exceeds other violence rates, reaching 5,509 cases (National Women's Commission, 2019). Victims of sexual violence are not only adults, but also minors (Desiningrum & Fauziah, 2018). Since 2018, most of sexual violence victims have been dominated by children, reaching 51.20 percent (Intan, 2018). Not only girls, but also boys, even in 2018, there more boys victims than girls, reaching 135 boys, and 42 girls (Setyawan, 2018).

One of the provinces in Indonesia which involve many children victims of sexual violence is Aceh (Indonesian Child Protection Commission, 2018), this has been alarming case since 2015. Based on data from the Integrated Service Center for Women's and Child Empowerment (P2TP2A) of Aceh Province in 2018, child sexual violence that occurred in Aceh reached 322 cases, can be seen in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Cases of child sexual violence in Aceh Province

Figure 1. explains that there were 203 child sexual abuse cases occurred in Aceh, 10 cases of incest, 8 cases of sodomy,

3 cases of trafficking, 2 cases of sexual exploitation, and 96 cases of rape (P2TP2A Rumoh Putroe Aceh, 2018). Most of these cases happened in Banda Aceh. Banda Aceh is one of the city in Aceh province which has a high rate of sexual violence from 2016 to 2017, and were the second highest of 23 districts or cities in Aceh for cases of sexual violence (Noviandi, 2018; Saniah, 2019). The victims ranges from 8-12 years old, this means that most victims of sexual violence are children who are in primary school and junior high school (Bahri & Fajriani, 2015).

Children, especially elementary school-age children are very vulnerable to sexual violence (Nevid, Rathus, & Greene, 2005). This is because their psychological conditions are not the same as adults. Children have not been able to be as rational as adults who can prevent and protect themselves from dangerous situations (Santrock, 2007), the personal safety skills possessed by children will be a great help for them to avoid the danger of sexual violence (Neherta, 2017; Brown-Goodyear, 2012). Personal safety skills are a set of skills that need to be mastered by children in order to maintain their own safety and avoid sexual violence (Bagley & King, 2004). Children who have personal safety skills have the ability to detect and handle situations that threaten them (James, Nelson, & Ashwill, 2013). They recognize potentially abusive situations, are able to withstand perpetrators' persuasion, report abusive situations, blaming the perpetrators, and not blaming himself, and report perpetrators (Wurtele & Owens, 1997; Kenny & Wurtele, 2008; in Brown-Goodyear, 2012).

One of the factors that affects personal safety skills is the knowledge possessed by the child himself. Knowledge that children have about sexual violence and how to protect themselves from sexual violence, and this knowledge will prevent them from becoming victims of sexual violence (Erogul & Hasirci, 2013). Based on their knowledge, children knew that no one could touch their private parts except themselves or their mother or the doctor who was examining them. Children also know that seduction given by someone without any interests will endanger them, so that they will quickly save themselves (Bagley & King, 2004; Erogul & Hasirci, 2013). Erogul and Hasirci (2013), in their research found that children who are skilled at protecting themselves from sexual violence are children who have knowledge related to it, children are able to recognize the characteristics of abusive situations, and know how to act to avoid sexual violence. These findings are different from the results of research from Kim and Kang (2016). Kim and Kang (2016) in their research found that children are able to protect

themselves from sexual violence even though they do not have adequate knowledge related to it.

Based on the description above, the purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between knowledge about protection from sexual violence with personal safety skills in elementary school students in Banda Aceh.

II. OBJECTIVES AND METHOD

The purpose of this study is to look at the relationship between knowledge and personal safety skills in elementary school students in Banda Aceh. The research subjects were 125 students from one of the elementary schools in Banda Aceh, who ranged from 9 to 11 years old. The samples were taken by using the simple random sampling technique. In this study, quantitative data is obtained through reliable and valid Personal Safety Skill Scales that have been tested, and also includes a Knowledge Test about Protection from Sexual Violence. The Personal Safety Skill Scale is based on the theory by Bagley and King (2004), which includes the recognize, resist, and report components. The scale in this research used statements with five Likert model choices of answer: Absolutely Agree (AA), Agree (A), Neutral (N), Not Agree (NA), and Absolutely Not Agree (ANA). The scores were moved from 1 to 5, and the scales were presented in the form of statements of favorable (support) and unfavorable (not support). Data were analyzed using Pearson correlation techniques.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results showed that there was a significant relationship between knowledge about protection from sexual violence with personal safety skills. This was verified by statistical analysis of correlation analysis which shows a significance value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) and the correlation $r_{\text{count}} = 0.552$ is greater than $r_{\text{table}} = 0.176$ ($r_{\text{count}} > r_{\text{table}}$), so the hypothesis of this research is accepted. This means the higher the knowledge of protection from sexual violence, then the higher the personal safety skills of elementary school students in Banda Aceh. This support the research conducted by Erogul and Hasirci (2013), that children who have knowledge about how to protect themselves will be skilled to maintain their safety from the threat of sexual violence.

The children's knowledge about how to protect themselves from sexual violence becomes a provision for them to be free from the threat of perpetrators of sexual violence (Finkelhor, 2009; Walsh, Zwi, Woolfenden, & Shlonsky, 2015). Because their knowledge make them able to distinguish body parts that should not be touched by just anyone (Barron & Topping, 2013; Neherta, 2017). If a child is seduced by someone without any interest, or is threatened to obey someone's request to do things that lead to sexual activity, then the child has awareness to avoid (Mashudi & Nur'aeni, 2015), and reports the events to adults they trusted (Barron & Topping, 2013; Erogul & Hasirci, 2013).

The results of this study are also in the same line with Bloom and Green's theory of behavior. Based on Bloom's theory (Notoatmodjo, 2003), knowledge is one of the very important domains in shaping one's behavior or actions.

Behavior that is based on knowledge will be more inherent and lasting than behavior that is not based on knowledge. Based on the theory of Green and Kreuter (1991), knowledge factors enter into predisposing factors that influence a person's behavior. The higher the level of knowledge of a person, the greater the opportunity for that person to behave.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study shows the relationship between knowledge about protection from sexual violence with personal safety skills in elementary school students in Banda Aceh. The higher the knowledge of how to protect themselves, the higher the personal safety skills of elementary school students in Banda Aceh. This finding can be used as a guide to conduct further research on factors that correlate with personal safety skills and make interventions to improve personal safety skills.

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